

Linking Destination Image and Event Quality with Tourist Satisfaction to Increase Tourism Loyalty in Sampang Regency

Pribanus Wantara¹, Alvin Sugeng Prasetyo²

¹ Management Department, Economic and Business Faculty, University of Trunojoyo Madura

² Economic Department, Economic and Business Faculty, University of Trunojoyo Madura

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
17 October 2024

Corresponding Author:
Pribanus Wantara

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine the structural relationship between destination image, event quality, tourist satisfaction, and tourist loyalty in the context of Madurese cultural arts performances in Sampang Regency, especially those held at Lon-Malang Beach, Toroan Beach and Camplong Beach. The proposed structural model relationship between variables was tested using structural equation modeling with data from 190 respondents utilizing the bootstrapping method. The study findings show a direct correlation between event quality and destination image with the level of tourist satisfaction during their visit to tourist loyalty. There is evidence that tourist satisfaction fully mediates the relationship between destination image and tourist loyalty. This study emphasizes the importance of including event quality in the tourism destination model, and shows that events such as Madurese cultural arts performances are an integral part of a marketing plan aimed at improving destination image, tourist satisfaction, and tourist loyalty.

KEYWORDS: Destination Image; Event Quality; Tourist Satisfaction; Tourist Loyalty

I. INTRODUCTION

In the tourism industry, factors that influence tourist satisfaction and loyalty are becoming increasingly relevant topics to study, especially in the context of destinations that offer special events. Destination image, Perceived value, and Event quality are important elements that contribute to the overall tourist experience. These three factors not only influence tourists' decisions to visit a particular destination but also determine their level of satisfaction and likelihood to return or recommend the destination to others.

Destination image plays an important role in building tourist expectations, where positive perceptions of a destination can increase attractiveness. Meanwhile, the value perceived by tourists, namely the comparison between the benefits obtained and the costs incurred, influences how they evaluate the travel experience. In addition, the quality of events held at the destination can have a significant impact on tourist satisfaction, especially when the events are well-designed and by visitor expectations. (Baloglu & McCleary, 1999) showed that destination image will influence tourists in choosing a destination and assessing the trip they have taken.

This article examines the relationship between destination image, event quality, and tourist satisfaction and its impact on their loyalty. By understanding these dynamics, destination

managers and event organizers can identify effective strategies to increase tourist loyalty, thereby contributing to the sustainability and growth of the tourism industry in the future.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Destination Image

Destination Image is a perception or mental picture that individuals have about a location or tourist destination, which is formed by various factors such as personal experiences, information received, promotions, and stories from others (Chenini & Cherif, 2016; Jenkins, 1999; Ozturk & Qu, 2008). This image includes elements such as natural beauty, culture, attractions, infrastructure, and the overall reputation of the destination. Destination Image greatly influences a person's travel decisions, because a positive image can attract visitors, while a negative image can deter interest in visiting. This destination image can also affect visitor satisfaction and their likelihood of recommending the place to others (Kusumah & Wahyudin, 2024; Puh, 2014; Ruiz et al., 2018).

Event Quality

Several authors state that Event Quality is a concept related to the perception of tourists or participants toward the quality of the experience provided by an event. Each study

highlights aspects that contribute to the assessment of the quality of an event, including services, facilities, and the overall experience provided. According to (Bitner & Hubbert, 1994; Moon et al., 2013), Event Quality includes various factors related to the event's organization, such as event management, service, physical facilities, and atmosphere. They emphasize that event quality is not only related to the content of the event itself but also to how the event is managed and delivered to participants. Aspects such as staff interaction, accessibility, comfort, and overall experience are the main indicators that influence tourists' perceptions of event quality. Meanwhile, according to (Fourie & Santana-Gallego, 2011) Event Quality is related to the attractiveness of the event in the context of tourism. They state that the quality of an event can be seen from its ability to attract tourists and provide unique experiences. High-quality events are able to create memorable experiences, which in turn increase tourist satisfaction with the event and the destination. Good event quality serves as an important tool in promoting tourism destinations globally.

Tourist Satisfaction

According to (Rust & Oliver, 1993; Rust & Zahorik, 1993), satisfaction is defined as a consumer's evaluation of the overall consumption experience, which is the result of a comparison between consumer expectations before consumption and their perceptions of actual performance or results after consumption. If the actual results match or exceed expectations, consumers will be satisfied; however, if the results do not match expectations, consumers will be dissatisfied. This definition emphasizes that satisfaction is an emotional response based on a comparison between expectations and reality, where positive or negative experiences will affect the level of consumer satisfaction. In a business context, customer satisfaction describes the extent to which a product or service provided by a company is able to meet or exceed consumer expectations. This satisfaction can affect loyalty and future purchasing behavior.

Tourist satisfaction is the level of pleasure or satisfaction felt by tourists after visiting a destination or attending an event, as a result of a comparison between expectations before the trip and the actual experience during the visit. This satisfaction plays an important role in determining tourist loyalty to a destination. (Oliver, 1997).

Tourist Loyalty

Loyalty is a person's commitment or loyalty to a party, be it an individual, organization, brand, or certain value, which is manifested through consistent actions and attitudes over a long period. Loyalty is often based on trust, a sense of responsibility, or satisfaction obtained from the relationship (Hsu & Cai, 2009). In a business context, customer loyalty reflects high customer satisfaction so that they continue to use products or services from the same company even though there are many other choices in the market. So, loyalty

includes emotional and rational elements that encourage someone to remain loyal and maintain their relationship with the party concerned. Tourist loyalty refers to the tendency of tourists to return to visit the same destination in the future and recommend it to others. Tourist loyalty can be formed through positive experiences, ongoing satisfaction, and emotional connections with the destination (Oliver, 1999).

Relationship between Destination Image and Tourist Satisfaction

When tourists have a positive image of a destination, such as natural beauty, rich culture, and good facilities, they tend to be more satisfied with their experience. A good image can increase their expectations before the visit and, if the actual experience matches or exceeds these expectations, the level of satisfaction will increase. Destination image shapes tourists' expectations about what they will experience. If these expectations are met or even exceeded during the visit, then tourist satisfaction will increase. Research shows that tourists' perceptions of a destination, including elements such as safety, cleanliness, and friendliness, can directly affect their experience and the level of satisfaction they feel (Chi & Qu, 2008; Gartner, 1994; Qu et al., 2011).

Tourists who are satisfied with their experience at a destination are more likely to recommend the destination to others and make repeat visits. Therefore, a good image and high satisfaction can support each other in building a destination's reputation (Kwortnik Jr & Thompson, 2009). Thus, these results raise the idea of a relationship between event quality and destination image:

H1. Destination image positively influences tourist satisfaction.

Relationship between Event Quality and Tourist Satisfaction

The relationship between Event Quality and Tourist Satisfaction refers to the influence of the quality of an event on the level of satisfaction of tourists attending the event. Event quality includes various aspects, such as service, facilities, event content, and the overall experience provided to participants. Good quality can increase tourist satisfaction because they feel they get value that is commensurate with the sacrifices they make (time, cost, and energy) to attend the event. The relationship between Event Quality and Tourist Satisfaction has been explained by several experts, including according to (Kwortnik Jr & Thompson, 2009), that good event quality directly contributes to tourist satisfaction, because tourists who attend an event expect a pleasant and well-structured experience. High event quality increases tourists' perceptions of the value they get, which in turn affects their satisfaction. Meanwhile, according to (Getz, 2008) in his research on Event Tourism, it is said event quality is an integral part of a destination's tourism strategy. Well-organized events, from content, and settings, to services, will improve the tourist experience. Furthermore,

“Linking Destination Image and Event Quality with Tourist Satisfaction to Increase Tourism Loyalty in Sampang Regency”

according to (Chen & Tsai, 2007) Event Quality plays an important role in shaping tourist satisfaction because quality events affect tourists' perceptions of the destination as a whole. Good quality of an event will increase tourist satisfaction, both directly through a pleasant experience during the event and indirectly through strengthening the positive image of the destination.

H2. Event quality positively affects tourist satisfaction.

Relationship between Destination Image and Tourist Loyalty

Chen & Tsai (2007) explained that Destination Image plays an important role in forming Tourist Loyalty. Furthermore, it is said that a positive image of a destination—which includes tourists' perceptions of beauty, facilities, culture, and service quality—will encourage tourist satisfaction. This satisfaction, in turn, is a key factor in creating tourist loyalty. Destination Image not only affects tourists' direct experiences but also how they reflect on those experiences after their visit. When tourists have a positive perception, they are more likely to return to the same destination (behavioral loyalty) and recommend the destination to others (attitudinal loyalty). Thus, a strong and positive image increases the likelihood of tourists becoming loyal customers or recommending the destination through word-of-mouth. According to Jenkins (1999) destination Image is a combination of subjective perceptions of tourists influenced by personal experiences, destination promotions, and information from third parties (such as recommendations from friends or reviews in the media). Thus, a positive and consistent image of a destination will greatly influence tourist loyalty. When tourists have a positive image before their visit, they will come with high expectations. If the image is proven to be in accordance with the experience they get, then loyalty to the destination will grow. Tourist Loyalty is formed when their actual experience is consistent with the positive image they previously imagined so that they feel confident to return to the destination or recommend it to others.

H3. Destination image positively influences Tourist Loyalty.

Relationship between Event Quality and Tourist Satisfaction

The relationship between Event Quality and Tourist Satisfaction is very strong. Good Event Quality, which includes services, facilities, atmosphere, and effective event management, can increase tourist satisfaction by providing a pleasant and valuable experience. Research from (Bitner & Hubbert, 1994; Chen & Tsai, 2007; Kwortnik Jr & Thompson, 2009; Moon et al., 2013) shows that the better the quality of an event, the greater the impact on tourists' satisfaction, which can ultimately increase tourist loyalty to the event and the related destination. Thus, it can be concluded that event quality has a positive effect on visitor satisfaction.

H4. Event quality has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction.

Relationship between Tourist Satisfaction and Tourist Loyalty

The relationship between Tourist Satisfaction and Tourist Loyalty explains how tourist satisfaction with their experience at a destination affects their loyalty to return or recommend the destination to others. When tourists are satisfied with their experience at a destination, whether in terms of facilities, services, attractions, or comfort, they are more likely to develop loyalty to that destination. High satisfaction motivates tourists to make repeat visits and continue to choose the same destination in the future or recommend the destination they have visited to friends, family, or online platforms. This recommendation is a strong indicator of tourist loyalty, where they are not only willing to return but also become advocates for the destination (Chi & Qu, 2008; Oliver, 1999; Y. Yoon & Uysal, 2005).

From this explanation, it can be concluded that tourist satisfaction is a key factor in building visitor loyalty, by making repeat visits or recommending destinations that have been visited to friends and family. So the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H5: Tourist Satisfaction has a positive effect on Tourist Loyalty.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

This study uses a quantitative approach with descriptive and explanatory research types. The quantitative approach is carried out from the process of data collection, analysis, and interpretation of research results (Creswell & John, 2018), while the explanatory approach is used to explain the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing (Neuman, 2007) and is used to explain the magnitude of the influence of Destination Image (X1), Event Quality (X2), Tourist Satisfaction (X3), on Tourist Loyalty (Y). This research model is depicted in Figure 1:

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

“Linking Destination Image and Event Quality with Tourist Satisfaction to Increase Tourism Loyalty in Sampang Regency”

Population and Sample

The population of this study was all visitors to the Beach in Sampang Regency (including Lon-Malang Beach, Camplong Beach, and Toroan Beach), and had visited at least once up to an infinite number, so that the population in this study is infinite (infinite population). Sampling was carried out using the Accidental Sampling/Convenience Sampling technique which is part of the Non Probability Sampling sample design (Sugiyono, 2010).

Data collection was carried out by determining the research subjects, namely all visitors to Lon-Malang Beach. Questionnaires were given to respondents in the amount of the sample. Data presentation was done in the form of a table using Ms. Excel as the raw data. Scoring used a Likert scale with 5 alternative answers, namely: Strongly Agree: 5, Agree: 4, Undecided: 2, Disagree: 2, Strongly Disagree: 1 (Cooper et al., 2003).

The subjects in this study were visitors to the tourist destinations of Lon-Malang Beach, Camplong Beach, and Toroan Beach. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed to all respondents who were visiting and enjoying events at Lon-Malang Beach, Camplong Beach, and Toroan Beach. The results of the questionnaire answers were then tabulated into Ms. Excel, then the data was analyzed using the SmartPLS 4.0 application.

respondents were used in this study, consisting of men (53.5%) and women (46.5%). Teenagers (62.6%) and adults (37.5%). Based on education level, respondents had Masters degrees (9%), Bachelor's degrees (55.8%), High School (32.5%), and Elementary School (2.8%). The majority of visitors were civil servants (33.3%), followed by private employees (29.8%), students (26.7%), and others (10.2%).

Validity and Reliability Test

There are two types of validity tests, namely Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity. The convergent validity test uses the outer loading (OL) and Average variance extraction (AVE) values (Hair Jr et al., 2017, 2021). An item is declared valid if it has an OL value above the threshold value of 0.7. Items that have an OL value below 0.5 are considered invalid, so they can affect the validity of the model content (AVE), so these items must be removed from the model (Hair Jr et al., 2021). In this study, all items in the model have an OL value higher than 0.5, so no items or indicators should be removed from the research model (see Figure 2 below). Figure 2 shows that the item OL value is far above the exploratory threshold value of 0.6, and therefore, it can be used to test the inner model (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

Furthermore, based on Table 1, the results show that the AVE value for each variable has a value greater than 0.5. So that all variables that support the model in this study are declared valid (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

From the 200 questionnaires distributed to visitors to the beach tourist destination, after being tabulated, only 190

Table 1. Reflective Measurement Model Results

Construct	Indicators	Loading	Rho_A	AVE	CR	Item_deleted
Destination Image	DI_1	0.731	0.805	0.556	0.862	None
	DI_2					
	DI_3					
	DI_4					
	DI_5					
Tourist Loyalty	TL_1	0.734	0.853	0.575	0.890	None
	TL_2	0.706				
	TL_3	0.794				
	TL_4	0.755				
	TL_5	0.789				
	TL_6	0.767				
Event Quality	EQ_1	0.775	0.784	0.594	0.854	None
	EQ_2	0.786				
	EQ_3	0.806				
	EQ_4	0.712				
Tourist Satisfaction	TS_1	0.872	0.821	0.727	0.889	None
	TS_2	0.855				
	TS_3	0.831				

Source: Smart_PLS processed data 4.0., 2024

“Linking Destination Image and Event Quality with Tourist Satisfaction to Increase Tourism Loyalty in Sampang Regency”

Reliability Test

The reliability test uses composite reliability values and Cronbach alpha functions as a test of the consistency of data and instrument feasibility, the reliability test can be seen from the Cronbach's alpha value or Composite Reliability (CR) value. To be able to say that a statement item is reliable, the Cronbach's alpha value must be greater than 0.6 and the Composite reliability (CR) value must be greater than 0.7 (Ghozali, 2016). The data shown in Table 1 shows that Cronbach's alpha value and the Composite reliability (CR) value have met the requirements so that the model is declared reliable to be used to analyze this research.

Table 2 R-Square

Variable	R-Square
Destination Image	0.466
Tourist Loyalty	0.672
Tourist Satisfaction	0.491

Source: Smart_PLS processed data 4.0., 2024

The results of the R-square test in Table 2 show that the Destination Image variable produces a value of 0.466, meaning that the destination image is supported by the quality of events held by the beach tourist destination by 46.6%, the remaining 53.4% is influenced by other factors or variables not included in this study. Furthermore, the R-square value for the tourist loyalty variable obtained a result of 0.672 or 67.2%, this result means that the tourist loyalty built by the beach tourist destination is influenced by event

Table 3. Summary of hypotheses testing results

Variable	Original sample	t-statistic	p-value	Description
Destination Image → Tourist Loyalty	0.411	8.842	0.000	Supported
Destination Image → Tourist Satisfaction	0.449	8.747	0.000	Supported
Event Quality → Destination Image	0.683	24.459	0.000	Supported
Event Quality → Tourist Loyalty	0.274	6.145	0.000	Supported
Event Quality → Tourist Satisfaction	0.312	5.619	0.000	Supported
Tourist Satisfaction → Tourist Loyalty	0.243	5.153	0.000	Supported
Destination Image → Tourist Loyalty	0.411	8.842	0.000	Supported

Based on Table 3, direct testing between variables can be explained as follows:

The first hypothesis that tests the effect of Destination Image on Tourist Loyalty produces an original sample value of 0.411, a t-statistic value of 8.842 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Destination Image has a significant effect on Tourist Loyalty. So the first hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (Bigne et al., 2001; Chi & Qu, 2008; Zhang et al., 2014).

The second hypothesis that tests the effect of Destination Image on Tourist Satisfaction obtained an original sample value of 0.449, a t-statistic value of 8.747 > 1.96, and a

quality, destination image, and tourist satisfaction by 67.2%, the remaining 32.8% is influenced by factors or variables outside this study. The R-square value for the Tourist Satisfaction variable obtained a value of 0.491, this result means that the tourist satisfaction variable is influenced by event quality by 49.1%, and the remaining 50.9% is influenced by factors or variables outside this study.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study uses the SmartPLS 4.0 application. Hypothesis testing can be done by considering the t-statistic and p-value for each variable. The rule of thumb used in this study is the beta coefficient (sample value) to determine the direction of the relationship, t-statistic value > 1.96, and p-value < 0.05 (5%). The results of hypothesis testing can be seen in Figure 2 and Table 3 below:

Fig. 2. The Results of Structural Equation Modelling
Source: Smart_PLS processed data 4.0., 2024

significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Destination Image has a positive and significant effect on Revisit intention, so the second hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (Beerli & Martin, 2004; Chen & Tsai, 2007; Kozak & Rimmington, 2000).

The third hypothesis that tests the effect of Event Quality on Destination Image, obtained an original sample value of 0.683, a t-statistic value of 24.459 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Event Quality has a positive and significant effect on Destination Image, so the third hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (Getz, 2008; J.-S. Lee et al., 2011).

“Linking Destination Image and Event Quality with Tourist Satisfaction to Increase Tourism Loyalty in Sampang Regency”

The fourth hypothesis that tests the effect of Event Quality on Tourist Loyalty produces an original sample value of 0.274, a t-statistic value of 6.145 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Event Quality has a significant effect on Destination Loyalty. So the fourth hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (J. Lee et al., 2012; Y. Yoon & Uysal, 2005).

The fifth hypothesis which tests the effect of Event Quality on Tourist Satisfaction, obtained an original sample value of 0.312, a t-statistic value of 5.619 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Event Quality has an effect on Tourist Satisfaction. So the fifth hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (Cole & Illum, 2006; J.-S. Lee et al., 2011; Y.-S. Yoon et al., 2010).

The sixth hypothesis that tests the effect of Tourist Satisfaction on Tourist Loyalty obtained an original sample value of 0.243, a t-statistic value of 5.153, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Tourist Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Tourist Loyalty, so the sixth hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (Prayag & Ryan, 2012; Y. Yoon & Uysal, 2005). The seventh hypothesis that tests the effect of Destination Image on Destination Loyalty, obtained an original sample value of 0.411, a t-statistic value of 8.842 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that Destination Image has a positive and significant effect on Tourist Loyalty. So the seventh hypothesis is accepted. These results support the research conducted (Chi & Qu, 2008; Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Ruiz et al., 2018).

For indirect effects, the results are shown in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4. Indirect Effects

Variable	Original sample	t-statistic	p-value
EQ → DI → TL	0.281	8.108	0.000
DI → TS → TL	0.109	4.684	0.000
EQ → TS → TL	0.076	3.600	0.000
EQ → DI → TS	0.307	7.454	0.000

The effect of Event Quality on Tourist Loyalty, mediated by Destination Image produces a t-statistic value of 8.108 > 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, this result concludes that Destination Image mediates the relationship between Event Quality and Destination Loyalty and the eighth hypothesis is accepted. These results support research conducted by (Konecnik & Gartner, 2007; Prayag & Ryan, 2012).

The effect of Destination Image on Tourist Loyalty mediated by Tourist Satisfaction, obtaining a t-statistic

value of 4.684 > 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, this result concludes that Tourist Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Destination Image and Tourist Loyalty, so the ninth hypothesis is accepted, this result supports the research conducted by (Gursoy & Rutherford, 2004; Y.-S. Yoon et al., 2010).

The effect of Event Quality on Tourist Loyalty mediated by Tourist Satisfaction, obtaining a t-statistic value of 3.600 > 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, this result concludes that Tourist satisfaction mediates the relationship between Event Quality and Tourist Loyalty, so the tenth hypothesis is accepted, this result supports the research conducted by (Gursoy & Rutherford, 2004; Jeong & Kim, 2020).

The effect of Event Quality on Tourist satisfaction mediated by Destination Image, obtained a t-statistic value of 7.454 > 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, these results conclude that Destination Image mediates the relationship between Event Quality and Tourist satisfaction, so that the eleventh hypothesis is accepted, these results support the research that has been conducted by (Jeong & Kim, 2020).

DISCUSSION

Managerial implications

At this time, especially after the end of the COVID-19 pandemic, all tourist destinations in the world are facing increasing competition and challenges (Chi & Qu, 2008), thus, it is important to understand what drives tourist behavior. From a practical perspective, our findings have important marketing implications for tourist destinations. Based on the results of the current study, we offer the following plan to maximize event quality and destination image because this strategy is expected to increase tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty.

First, the study results show that event quality helps destination managers understand the factors that contribute to destination image, tourist satisfaction, and ultimately Tourist loyalty.

Furthermore, we suggest that destination managers and event organizers consider these four latent dimensions of event quality to ensure that event travelers' needs and desires for a vacation are met. To improve event quality, event organizers should strive to present events that are of interest and interest to tourists. In addition, efforts should be made to offer tourists a variety of performances and events. Intuitively, enjoyable events, such as musical performances, enhance tourists' experience and event satisfaction and increase the likelihood of revisiting the destination and recommending the destination to family, friends, and acquaintances. To improve event quality, volunteers should be trained and educated to create the right attitude; friendly smiles, and friendly attitudes during events held at the tourist destination, thereby enhancing tourists' image of the

destination (Jin et al., 2013). Regarding environmental quality, destination managers should pay more attention to tourists' safety.

The current study confirms that destination image is positively related to tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty, highlighting the important contribution that destination image makes to the development of individual satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, improving the image of a tourist destination in the eyes of tourists should be a management goal. Tourist destination managers can improve the image of a tourist destination by utilizing social media. According to (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010), social media such as YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook are internet-based applications that are able to create and share customer experiences, ideas, and opinions with the general public. Because in general tourists always rely on social media to obtain specific information about a tourist destination before visiting (Habibi et al., 2014; Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014). Therefore, tourist destination marketers must utilize social media as a promotional tool to improve the image of a tourist destination.

Research implications

This study advances the knowledge of nature tourism by investigating the relationships among event quality, destination image, tourist satisfaction, and Tourist loyalty. Findings suggest that event quality has a direct effect on destination image and tourist satisfaction. Destination image is an important factor in stimulating tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty. The relationship between tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty is positive and significant. Furthermore, they suggest that the path from destination image to destination loyalty to destination loyalty is entirely dependent on tourist satisfaction. From a theoretical perspective, this study offers several implications for research in marketing and tourism. First, this study embraces (Jin et al., 2013) argument and call by seeking to understand the role of event quality in the context of event management. More specifically, the authors note that event quality is a key consideration of event marketing strategies that focus on customer retention. They call for further research in other event settings to ensure the external validity of event quality measures, which could be useful and helpful to the event management literature. With their call, we describe four dimensions (game quality, interaction quality, outcome quality, and physical environment quality) to accurately reflect event quality characteristics, and we evaluate convergent validity (e.g., factor loadings, CR, and AVE); as a result, its validity is satisfactory.

With satisfactory validity for event quality, this study examines the relationship between event quality and destination image and shows that event quality acts as an antecedent of destination image and is in line with previous studies (Tosun et al., 2015). Therefore, tourism researchers

and marketers should not underestimate the importance of event quality in predicting destination image.

Second, the current study responds to the recent call for marketing or tourism researchers to conduct an integrative model (Prayag et al., 2017). More specifically, to develop a stable event quality model, we include tourist satisfaction in the proposed model. In the early event quality studies, (Sung Moon et al., 2011) examined the theoretical relationship between event quality and destination image, and based on that study, (Moon et al., 2013) tested service quality, destination image, and behavioral intention. In the same year, (Jin et al., 2013) examined whether event quality and destination image determine visitors' future behavioral intentions. Although these studies build the necessary foundation for event quality, they do not adequately focus on the importance of tourist satisfaction. A recent study stated that "if tourists highly value a product or service provided at an event, they are more likely to have a high level of satisfaction" (Jeong et al., 2019). In line with previous studies (Han & Hyun, 2017; Theodorakis et al., 2015), the results also confirm that event quality has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is clearly important for researchers and marketers to better understand the key relationships between event quality and satisfaction in the context of event management.

The third implication is that this study provides empirical evidence on the relationship between destination loyalty formation and destination image and tourist satisfaction. Previous authors have argued that destination image and tourist satisfaction are closely related to destination loyalty (Gursoy et al., 2014; C.-K. Lee et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2014). However, others have stated that destination loyalty does not guarantee that tourists will revisit the destination because they tend to choose a new location even though they have had a satisfying and positive experience (Trang, 2018). Furthermore, ((Chi & Qu, 2008) argued that destination loyalty has no relationship with destination image. Nevertheless, this study reveals and confirms the existence of a significant relationship between destination image, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty, and thus, our findings suggest that it would be beneficial for destination marketers to invest more in events to build tourist loyalty. The fourth implication is that this study contributes to tourism research by exploring the mediating effect of tourist satisfaction between destination image and destination loyalty. In the broader tourism context, previous studies have consistently suggested that tourist satisfaction mediates the relationship between destination image and loyalty (Hernández-Lobato et al., 2006), and our results also identify an indirect relationship between destination image and destination loyalty through tourist satisfaction, which is consistent with previous empirical research (Jeong & Kim, 2019). In particular, these results suggest that tourist satisfaction has a full mediation effect, which has not been reported in previous studies.

Although the positive effects of small-scale events, such as marathons, are recognized, relatively little research has been conducted on the topic. In this regard, our findings contribute to the nature tourism literature by confirming the significant impact of event quality, and destination image generated by small-scale events on tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty, and suggesting that these events should be considered important in terms of achieving competitive advantage.

IV. CONCLUSION

As we have seen, the main objective of this study was to investigate the structural relationships between quality, destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty with an emphasis on the mediating effect of tourist satisfaction on the relationship between destination image and destination loyalty, in the context of small-scale events. The findings show significant impacts of event quality on destination image; event quality, and destination image on tourist satisfaction; destination image, and tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty; and show that tourist satisfaction fully mediates the relationship between destination image and event quality on destination loyalty. Based on the results, the contributions of this study are to combine quality and value in the tourism destination image-satisfaction-loyalty model; provide empirical evidence that tourist satisfaction fully mediates the relationship between destination image and destination loyalty, and destination loyalty in the nature tourism industry; and confirm that both small-scale and large-scale events should be considered important to sustain the success of tourism destinations. Although this study highlights the benefits of using an integrated approach to enhance event quality, destination image, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty, it has several limitations. First, we did not investigate other exogenous variables, including the positive impact of expectations. Additional research is needed to explore the effects of more of these variables to broaden the understanding of the forces driving tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty (e.g., using event image, perceived risk, destination familiarity and identification, and novelty seeking as potential variables). Second, satisfaction is examined as a potential mediator of the relationship between destination image and destination loyalty. However, the effects of other potential mediators (e.g. place attachment) should be investigated to provide a more comprehensive framework. Third, our research findings may not be applicable to other tourist destinations because each destination has different tourism characteristics. Our findings may not be generalizable, so similar studies are needed for other tourist destinations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to express our gratitude to University of Trunojoyo Madura for providing research grant funding for the 2024 budget. We also thank the Sampang Regency Government, all parties who have helped during the research process, and all staff who participated in this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Baloglu, S., & McCleary, K. W. (1999). A model of destination image formation. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 26(4), 868–897.
2. Beerli, A., & Martin, J. D. (2004). Factors influencing destination image. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(3), 657–681.
3. Bigne, J. E., Sanchez, M. I., & Sanchez, J. (2001). Tourism image, evaluation variables and after purchase behaviour: inter-relationship. *Tourism Management*, 22(6), 607–616.
4. Bitner, M. J., & Hubbert, A. R. (1994). Encounter satisfaction versus overall satisfaction versus quality: the customer's voice. *Service Quality: New Directions in Theory and Practice*, 72–94.
5. Chen, C.-F., & Tsai, D. (2007). How destination image and evaluative factors affect behavioral intentions? *Tourism Management*, 28(4), 1115–1122.
6. Chenini, A., & Cherif, N.-E. (2016). Factors influencing image of tourist destination: integrated marketing communications approach; conceptualization and retrospective re-debate. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management (IJARM)*, 5(1), 1747–2296.
7. Chi, C. G.-Q., & Qu, H. (2008). Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach. *Tourism Management*, 29(4), 624–636.
8. Cole, S. T., & Illum, S. F. (2006). Examining the mediating role of festival visitors' satisfaction in the relationship between service quality and behavioral intentions. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 12(2), 160–173. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356766706062156>
9. Cooper, D. R., Schindler, P. S., Cooper, D. R., & Schindler, P. S. (2003). *Business research methods*.
10. Creswell, J. D., & John, W. (2018). Creswell, research design. qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. *Fifth. London*.
11. Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. R. B. (2003). The meaning and measurement of destination image: [Reprint of original article published in v. 2, no. 2, 1991: 2-12.]. *Journal of Tourism Studies*, 14(1), 37–48.

12. Fourie, J., & Santana-Gallego, M. (2011). The impact of mega-sport events on tourist arrivals. *Tourism Management, 32*(6), 1364–1370.
13. Gartner, W. C. (1994). Image formation process. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing, 2*(2–3), 191–216.
14. Getz, D. (2008). Event tourism: Definition, evolution, and research. *Tourism Management, 29*(3), 403–428.
15. Ghozali, I. (2016). Desain penelitian kuantitatif dan kualitatif untuk akuntansi, bisnis, dan ilmu sosial lainnya. *Semarang: Yoga Pratama*.
16. Gursoy, D., & Rutherford, D. G. (2004). Host attitudes toward tourism: An Improved Structural Model. *Annals of Tourism Research, 31*(3), 495–516. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2003.08.008>
17. Gursoy, D., S. Chen, J., & G. Chi, C. (2014). Theoretical examination of destination loyalty formation. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management, 26*(5), 809–827.
18. Habibi, M. R., Laroche, M., & Richard, M.-O. (2014). The roles of brand community and community engagement in building brand trust on social media. *Computers in Human Behavior, 37*, 152–161.
19. Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: A workbook*. Springer Nature.
20. Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Gudergan, S. P. (2017). *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling*. saGe publications.
21. Han, H., & Hyun, S. S. (2017). Impact of hotel-restaurant image and quality of physical-environment, service, and food on satisfaction and intention. *International Journal of Hospitality Management, 63*, 82–92.
22. Hernández-Lobato, L., Solis-Radilla, M. M., Moliner-Tena, M. A., & Sánchez-García, J. (2006). Tourism destination image, satisfaction and loyalty: a study in Ixtapa-Zihuatanejo, Mexico. *Tourism Geographies, 8*(4), 343–358.
23. Hsu, C., & Cai, L. A. (2009). Brand knowledge, trust and loyalty-a conceptual model of destination branding. *International CHRIE Conference-Refereed Track, 12*.
24. Jenkins, O. H. (1999). Understanding and measuring tourist destination images. *International Journal of Tourism Research, 1*(1), 1–15.
25. Jeong, Y., & Kim, S. (2019). Exploring a suitable model of destination image: The case of a small-scale recurring sporting event. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics, 31*(5), 1287–1307.
26. Jeong, Y., & Kim, S. (2020). A study of event quality, destination image, perceived value, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty among sport tourists. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics, 32*(4), 940–960. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-02-2019-0101>
27. Jeong, Y., Kim, S.-K., & Yu, J.-G. (2019). Determinants of behavioral intentions in the context of sport tourism with the aim of sustaining sporting destinations. *Sustainability, 11*(11), 3073.
28. Jin, N., Lee, H., & Lee, S. (2013). Event quality, perceived value, destination image, and behavioral intention of sports events: The case of the IAAF World Championship, Daegu, 2011. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research, 18*(8), 849–864.
29. Konecnik, M., & Gartner, W. C. (2007). Customer-based brand equity for a destination. *Annals of Tourism Research, 34*(2), 400–421. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2006.10.005>
30. Kozak, M., & Rimmington, M. (2000). Tourist satisfaction with Mallorca, Spain, as an off-season holiday destination. *Journal of Travel Research, 38*(3), 260–269.
31. Kusumah, E. P., & Wahyudin, N. (2024). Sporting event quality: destination image, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty. *Event Management, 28*(1), 59–74.
32. Kwortnik Jr, R. J., & Thompson, G. M. (2009). Unifying service marketing and operations with service experience management. *Journal of Service Research, 11*(4), 389–406.
33. Lee, C.-K., Yoon, Y.-S., & Lee, S.-K. (2007). Investigating the relationships among perceived value, satisfaction, and recommendations: The case of the Korean DMZ. *Tourism Management, 28*(1), 204–214.
34. Lee, J., Kyle, G., & Scott, D. (2012). The mediating effect of place attachment on the relationship between festival satisfaction and loyalty to the festival hosting destination. *Journal of Travel Research, 51*(6), 754–767.
35. Lee, J.-S., Lee, C.-K., & Choi, Y. (2011). Examining the role of emotional and functional values in festival evaluation. *Journal of Travel Research, 50*(6), 685–696.
36. Moon, K.-S., Ko, Y. J., Connaughton, D. P., & Lee, J.-H. (2013). A mediating role of destination image in the relationship between event quality, perceived value, and behavioral intention. *Journal of Sport & Tourism, 18*(1), 49–66.
37. Neuman, W. L. (2007). *Basics of social research*.
38. Oliver, R. L. (1997). Satisfaction, a behavioral perspective on the consumer. the mcgrawhill companies. *Inc., New York*.
39. Oliver, R. L. (1999). Whence consumer loyalty? *Journal of Marketing, 63*(4_suppl1), 33–44.

“Linking Destination Image and Event Quality with Tourist Satisfaction to Increase Tourism Loyalty in Sampang Regency”

40. Ozturk, A. B., & Qu, H. (2008). The impact of destination images on tourists' perceived value, expectations, and loyalty. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 9(4), 275–297.
41. Prayag, G., Hosany, S., Muskat, B., & Del Chiappa, G. (2017). Understanding the relationships between tourists' emotional experiences, perceived overall image, satisfaction, and intention to recommend. *Journal of Travel Research*, 56(1), 41–54.
42. Prayag, G., & Ryan, C. (2012). Antecedents of tourists' loyalty to Mauritius: The role and influence of destination image, place attachment, personal involvement, and satisfaction. *Journal of Travel Research*, 51(3), 342–356.
43. Puh, B. (2014). Destination image and tourism satisfaction: The case of a Mediterranean destination. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(13), 538–544.
44. Qu, H., Kim, L. H., & Im, H. H. (2011). A model of destination branding: Integrating the concepts of the branding and destination image. *Tourism Management*, 32(3), 465–476.
45. Ruiz, E. de los R. C., González, G. J. B., & Zamora, D. T. (2018). Destination image, satisfaction and destination loyalty in cruise tourism: the case of Malaga (Spain). *Tourism & Management Studies*, 14(1), 58–68.
46. Rust, R. T., & Oliver, R. L. (1993). *Service quality: New directions in theory and practice*. Sage Publications.
47. Rust, R. T., & Zahorik, A. J. (1993). Customer satisfaction, customer retention, and market share. *Journal of Retailing*, 69(2), 193–215.
48. Sugiyono, S. (2010). Metode penelitian kuantitatif dan kualitatif dan R&D. *Alfabeta Bandung*.
49. Sung Moon, K., Kim, M., Jae Ko, Y., Connaughton, D. P., & Hak Lee, J. (2011). The influence of consumer's event quality perception on destination image. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 21(3), 287–303.
50. Theodorakis, N. D., Kaplanidou, K., & Karabaxoglou, I. (2015). Effect of event service quality and satisfaction on happiness among runners of a recurring sport event. *Leisure Sciences*, 37(1), 87–107.
51. Tosun, C., Dedeoğlu, B. B., & Fyall, A. (2015). Destination service quality, affective image and revisit intention: The moderating role of past experience. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 4(4), 222–234.
52. Trang, N. T. (2018). The effects of senses and emotions on tourist experience and destination image. *Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Seoul: Kyung Hee University*.
53. Xiang, Z., & Gretzel, U. (2010). Role of social media in online travel information search. *Tourism Management*, 31(2), 179–188.
54. Yoon, Y., & Uysal, M. (2005). An examination of the effects of motivation and satisfaction on destination loyalty: a structural model. *Tourism Management*, 26(1), 45–56.
55. Yoon, Y.-S., Lee, J.-S., & Lee, C.-K. (2010). Measuring festival quality and value affecting visitors' satisfaction and loyalty using a structural approach. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(2), 335–342. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2009.10.002>
56. Zeng, B., & Gerritsen, R. (2014). What do we know about social media in tourism? A review. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 10, 27–36.
57. Zhang, H., Fu, X., Cai, L. A., & Lu, L. (2014). Destination image and tourist loyalty: A meta-analysis. *Tourism Management*, 40, 213–223.